

A Theoretical Study of the Relationships between Electronic Structure and 5-HT_{1A} and 5-HT_{2A} Receptor Binding Affinity of a group of ligands containing an isonicotinic nucleus

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Abstract A formal quantum-chemical analysis of the relationships between the electronic structure of two series of isonicotinamide derivatives and their 5-HT_{1A} and 5-HT_{1B} receptor binding affinities was carried out. The electronic structure was calculated at the B3LYP/6-31G(d,p) after full geometry optimization. Statistically significant relationships were obtained for the four cases. The analysis of the results suggests what modifications of the molecules could be useful to raise receptor affinity. The partial 2D pharmacophores for the binding to each receptor suggest that both, 5-HT_{1A} and 5-HT_{2A}, seem to have a site that is rich in sigma electrons.

Keywords Serotonin, QSAR, KPG method, 5-HT_{1A}, 5-HT_{2A}, pharmacophore, reactivity indices

Introduction

Serotonin receptors are a group of G protein-coupled receptors and ligand-gated ion channels found in the central and peripheral nervous systems. As their subtypes and effects have been discussed in previous publications, we refer the reader to the literature [1, 2]. Some of the main latest advances that deserve to be mentioned are in Refs. [3-9]. From a longtime our Unit has been studying the relationships between electronic structure and serotonergic receptor(s) binding affinity in structurally different groups of molecules [1, 2, 10-20]. As a new effort to get more information about these systems, we present here the results of quantum chemical study of the relationships between 5-HT_{1A} and 5-HT_{2A} receptor binding affinity and the electronic structure of a series of isonicotinamide derivatives.

Methods, models and calculations

The molecules were selected from a recent study[21]. They are shown in Figs. 1 and 2, and Tables 1 and 2[21]. The biological activity studied here is the in vitro affinity for serotonin 5HT_{1A} and 5HT_{2A} receptors measured in rat brain cortex with radioligand binding assays (³H]8-OH-DPAT for 5HT_{1A} receptors and [³H] ketanserin for 5HT_{2A} receptors), expressed as IC₅₀[21].

Figure 1: General structure of molecules of Group A

Table 1: Structure and receptor affinities of Group A [21].

Mol.	Mol.	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	log(IC ₅₀) 5HT _{1A}	log(IC ₅₀) 5HT _{2A}
1	3a	H	H	H	0.94	2.30
2	3b	OMe	H	H	-0.44	2.77
3	3c	H	H	OMe	3.10	2.96
4	3d	OCH ₂ CH ₃	H	H	0.68	1.21
5	3e	CN	H	H	1.18	1.74
6	3f	CH ₃	H	H	2.74	2.80
7	3g	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	1.22	1.85
8	3h	Cl	H	H	0.45	2.67
9	3i	H	Cl	H	-0.09	1.55
10	3j	H	H	Cl	2.52	2.82
11	3k	H	Cl	Cl	2.66	0.99
12	3l	F	H	H	1.03	-1.90
13	3m	H	H	F	2.74	-1.34
14	3n	H	H	H	0.03	-
15	3o	-*	H	H	2.20	3.44
16	3t	H	H	H	0.72	1.62

*:N instead of C.

*Figure 2: General structure of molecules of Group B***Table 2:** Structure and receptor affinities of Group B [21].

Mol.	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	log(IC ₅₀) 5HT _{1A}	log(IC ₅₀) 5HT _{2A}
1	H	H	H	1.75	2.05
2	OMe	H	H	1.14	-0.60
3	H	H	OMe	1.39	3.10
4	OCH ₂ CH ₃	H	H	0.98	2.32
5	CN	H	H	2.09	2.26
6	CH ₃	H	H	3.52	-
7	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	0.93	2.89
8	Cl	H	H	2.09	1.97
9	H	Cl	H	2.77	3.14
10	H	H	Cl	2.51	0.55
11	H	Cl	Cl	2.34	0.03
12	F	H	H	2.52	-1.41
13	H	H	F	2.00	-0.64
14	H	H	H	2.00	2.90
15	-*	H	H	0.96	-2.01
16	H	H	H	3.03	-

*:N instead of C.

To relate structure with activity we employed the formal KGP (Klopman-Peradejordi-Gómez) method [22]. As this technique has been the subject of a recent full review we refer the reader to the literature [23-30]. In summary, any

biological activity is related through a linear equation to a set of local atomic reactivity indices and the orientational parameters of the substituents. The applications of the KPG method to diverse biological activities and molecule during 2016-2017 showed its superiority over the empirical QSAR methods [2, 31-45].

The electronic structure of all molecules in their protonated form was calculated with the Density Functional Theory at the B3LYP/6-31G(d,p) level after full geometry optimization. The Gaussian suite of programs was used [46]. The numerical values for the LARIs were calculated from information inside the Gaussian results file with the D-Cent-QSAR software [47]. All the electron populations smaller than or equal to 0.01 e were considered as zero [24]. Negative electron populations coming from Mulliken Population Analysis were corrected as usual [48]. Orientational parameters were taken from published Tables or calculated as usual [49-51]. Given that the resolution of the system of linear equations is not possible because we have not enough experimental data, we employed Linear Multiple Regression Analysis (LMRA) techniques to find the best solution. For each case, a matrix containing the dependent variable ($\log(\text{IC}_{50})$) and the local atomic reactivity indices of all atoms of the common skeleton as independent variables was built. The Statistica software was used for LMRA [52].

Results

Results for Group A

Figure 3 shows the common skeleton numbering of Group A that will be employed in the results and discussion.

Figure 3: Common skeleton numbering for Group A

Results for the 5-HT_{1A} receptor binding affinity of Group A.

The best equation obtained is:

$$\log(\text{IC}_{50}) = 37.37 + 0.02\phi_4 + 0.50S_{19}^E - 30.5S_{12}^E(\text{HOMO}-2)^* - 168.20F_4(\text{LUMO})^* \quad (1)$$

with $n=13$, $R=0.98$, $R^2=0.96$, $\text{adj-}R^2=0.94$, $F(4,8)=49.23$ ($p<0.00001$) and a standard error of estimate of 0.23. No outliers were detected and no residuals fall outside the $\pm 2\sigma$ limits. Here, ϕ_4 is the orientational parameter of R_4 , S_{19}^E is the total atomic electrophilic superdelocalizability of atom 19, $S_{12}^E(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$ is the electrophilic superdelocalizability of the third highest occupied molecular orbital localized on atom 12 and $F_4(\text{LUMO})^*$ is the Fukui index (electron population) of the lowest empty MO localized on atom 4. Tables 3 and 4 show the beta coefficients, the results of the t-test for significance of coefficients and the matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables of Eq. 1. There are no significant internal correlations between independent variables (Table 4). Figure 4 displays the plot of observed vs. calculated $\log(\text{IC}_{50})$.

Table 3: Beta coefficients and t-test for significance of coefficients in Eq. 1

Variable	Beta	t(8)	p-level
ϕ_4	0.64	8.86	0.00002
S_{19}^E	0.22	2.94	0.019
$S_{12}^E(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$	-0.47	-6.30	0.0002
$F_4(\text{LUMO})^*$	-0.29	-3.56	0.0074

Table 4: Matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables in Eq. 1

	φ_4	S_{19}^E	$S_{12}^E(\text{HOMO-2})^*$	$F_4(\text{LUMO})^*$
φ_4	1.00			
S_{19}^E	0.00	1.00		
$S_{12}^E(\text{HOMO-2})^*$	0.00	0.01	1.00	
$F_4(\text{LUMO})^*$	0.06	0.11	0.07	1.00

Figure 4: Plot of predicted vs. observed $\log(\text{IC}_{50})$ values (Eq. 1). Dashed lines denote the 95% confidence interval. The associated statistical parameters of Eq. 1 indicate that this equation is statistically significant and that the variation of the numerical values of a group of four local atomic reactivity indices of atoms of the common skeleton explains about 94% of the variation of $\log(\text{IC}_{50})$. Figure 4, spanning about 3.5 orders of magnitude, shows that there is a good correlation of observed *versus* calculated values and that almost all points are inside the 95% confidence interval.

Results for the 5-HT_{2A} receptor binding affinity of Group A

The best equation obtained is:

$$\log(\text{IC}_{50}) = -17.44 - 11.99S_8^E(\text{HOMO} - 1)^* - 72.14F_{15}(\text{HOMO} - 2)^* - 2.06\mu_{10} + 0.24S_{23}^N(\text{LUMO} + 2)^* + 1.52F_{21}(\text{HOMO} - 1)^* \quad (2)$$

with $n=14$, $R=0.99$, $R^2=0.99$, $\text{adj-}R^2=0.98$, $F(5,8)=147.63$ ($p<0.000001$) and a standard error of estimate of 0.20. No outliers were detected and no residuals fall outside the $\pm 2\sigma$ limits. Here, $S_8^E(\text{HOMO-1})^*$ is the electrophilic superdelocalizability of the second highest occupied MO localized on atom 8, $F_{15}(\text{HOMO-2})^*$ is the Fukui index of the third occupied MO localized on atom 15, μ_{10} is the local atomic electronic chemical potential of atom 10, $S_{23}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$ is the nucleophilic superdelocalizability of the third empty MO localized on atom 23 and $F_{21}(\text{HOMO-1})^*$ is the Fukui index of the second highest occupied MO localized on atom 21. Tables 5 and 6 show the beta coefficients, the results of the t-test for significance of coefficients and the matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables of Eq. 2. There are no significant internal correlations between independent variables (Table 6). Figure 5 displays the plot of observed *vs.* calculated $\log(\text{IC}_{50})$.

Table 5: Beta coefficients and t-test for significance of coefficients in Eq. 2

Variable	Beta	t(8)	p-level
$S_8^E(\text{HOMO-1})^*$	-0.82	-20.81	0.0000001
$F_{15}(\text{HOMO-2})^*$	-0.70	-16.93	0.0000001
μ_{10}	-0.26	-6.57	0.0002
$S_{23}^N(\text{LUMO+2})^*$	0.30	6.68	0.0002
$F_{21}(\text{HOMO-1})^*$	0.17	3.73	0.006

Table 6: Matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables in Eq. 2

	$S_8^E(\text{HOMO-1})^*$	μ_{10}	$F_{15}(\text{HOMO-2})^*$	$F_{21}(\text{HOMO-1})^*$
μ_{10}	0.02	1.00		
$F_{15}(\text{HOMO-2})^*$	0.01	0.07	1.00	
$F_{21}(\text{HOMO-1})^*$	0.05	0.03	0.09	1.00
$S_{23}^N(\text{LUMO+2})^*$	0.07	0.05	0.04	0.14

Figure 5: Plot of predicted vs. observed $\log(IC_{50})$ values (Eq. 2). Dashed lines denote the 95% confidence interval

The associated statistical parameters of Eq. 2 indicate that this equation is statistically significant and that the variation of the numerical values of a group of five local atomic reactivity indices of atoms of the common skeleton explains about 98% of the variation of the receptor affinity. Figure 5, spanning about five orders of magnitude, shows that there is a good correlation of observed *versus* calculated values and that almost all points are inside the 95% confidence interval.

Local Molecular Orbitals

Table 7 shows the local molecular orbitals of atoms 4, 8 and 12. Table 8 shows the local molecular orbitals of atoms 15, 21 and 23 (see Fig. 3). Nomenclature: Molecule (HOMO) / (HOMO-2)* (HOMO-1)* (HOMO)* - (LUMO)* (LUMO+1)* (LUMO+2)*.

Table 7: Local Molecular Orbitals of atoms 4, 8 and 12

Molecule	Atom 4 (C)	Atom 8 (O)	Atom 12 (H)
1 (83)	79π80π81σ-84π85π88π	79π80π81π-84π86π88π	67σ68σ76σ-84σ86σ89σ
2 (91)	86π88π89σ-92π93π97π	86π88π89π-92π95π97π	63σ73σ74σ-92σ94σ95σ
3 (91)	86π87π89σ-92π93π96π	86π87π89π-92π94π95π	73σ74σ84σ-92σ94σ95σ
4 (95)	91π92π93σ-96π97π99σ	91π92π93π-96π98π99π	74σ75σ88σ-96σ98σ100σ
5 (89)	85π86π88σ-90π92π93π	85π86π88π-90π94π95π	71σ73σ82σ-90σ94σ95σ
6 (87)	82π83π85σ-88π89π93π	82π83π85π-88π90π92π	68σ69σ80σ-88σ90σ93σ
7 (91)	86π87π89σ-92π93π97π	86π87π89π-92π94π95π	70σ72σ84σ-92σ94σ97σ
8 (91)	87π88π89σ-92π93π97π	87π88π89π-92π96π97π	73σ74σ84σ-92σ94σ96σ
9 (91)	87π88π89σ-92π93π97π	87π88π89π-92π95π96π	73σ74σ83σ-92σ95σ96σ
10 (91)	86π88π89σ-92π93π96π	86π88π89π-92π94π95π	72σ74σ83σ-92σ94σ95σ
11 (99)	94π96π97σ-100π101π105π	94π96π97π-100π103π104π	80σ82σ90σ-100σ103σ104σ
12 (87)	83π86σ87σ-88π89π93π	83π86π87π-88π92π93π	71σ72σ80σ-88σ92σ93σ
13 (87)	82π84π85σ-88π89π93π	82π84π85π-88π90π91π	71σ72σ80σ-88σ90σ91σ
14 (83)	79π80π82σ-84π85π86π	79π80π82π-84π88π89π	64σ66σ67σ-84σ87σ88σ
15 (83)	79π80π81σ-84π86π88π	79π80π81π-84π88π89π	67σ68σ77σ-84σ87σ88σ
16 (96)	91π92π93σ-97π99π102π	91π92π93π-97π100π102π	74σ76σ88σ-97σ100σ102σ

Table 8: Local Molecular Orbitals of atoms 15, 21 and 23

Molecule	Atom 15 (C)	Atom 21 (C)	Atom 23 (C)	Atom 24 (C)
1 (83)	75σ78σ83σ- 86σ87σ88σ	78π82π83π- 86π87π88π	78π82π83π- 87π88π89π	78σ82π83π- 86π87π88π
2 (91)	78σ87σ91σ- 94σ98σ100σ	87π90π91π- 94π95π96π	87π90π91π- 95π96π98π	87π90π91σ- 94π95π96π
3 (91)	82σ88σ91σ- 94σ97σ101σ	88π90π91π- 94π95π97π	88π90π91π- 94π95π96π	88π90π91π- 94π95π97π
4 (95)	83σ86σ90σ- 103σ104σ105σ	90π94π95π- 98π99π101π	90π94π95π- 99π100π101π	90σ94π95π- 98π99π100π
5 (89)	77σ83σ84σ- 93σ96σ97σ	84π87π89π- 91π92π93π	84π87π89π- 91π93π102π	84σ87π89π- 91π92π93π
6 (87)	77σ79σ84σ- 92σ95σ96σ	79σ84π86π- 90π91π92π	84σ86π87π- 91π92π93π	84σ86π87π- 90π91π92π
7 (91)	81σ82σ88σ- 95σ96σ99σ	88π90π91π- 94π95π96π	88π90π91π- 94π95π96π	88σ90π91σ- 94π95π96π
8 (91)	78σ80σ86σ- 94σ100σ101σ	83σ86π90π- 94π95π96π	86π90π91π- 94π95π96π	86σ90π91σ- 94π95π96π
9 (91)	82σ86σ91σ- 94σ95σ99σ	86π90π91π- 94π96π99π	86π90π91π- 94π95π96π	86π90π91π- 94π95π96π
10 (91)	81σ82σ87σ- 99σ101σ102σ	87π90π91π- 94π95π96π	87π90π91π- 94π95π96π	87π90π91π- 94π95π96π
11 (99)	88σ95σ99σ- 102σ103σ108σ	95σ98π99π- 102π103π104π	95π98π99π- 102π103π104π	95π98π99π- 102π103π104π
12 (87)	79σ84σ87σ- 90σ94σ96σ	84π85π87σ- 90π91π99σ	85π86π87σ- 90π91π105π	84π85π87σ- 90π91π100σ
13 (87)	76σ78σ83σ- 95σ96σ98σ	83π86π87π- 90π91π92π	83π86π87π- 90π91π92π	83σ86π87π- 90π91π92π
14 (83)	75σ76σ83σ- 87σ92σ93σ	77π78π81σ- 85π86π87π	78π81σ83π- 85π86π87π	78π81σ83π- 85π86π87π
15 (83)	75σ82σ83σ- 88σ91σ92σ	76π82σ83π- 85π87π88π	76π82σ83π- 85π87π88π	76π82σ83π- 85π87π88π
16 (96)	90σ94σ96σ- 98σ104σ106σ	94π95π96π- 98π101π105π	90π94π95π- 101π105π109π	94π95π96π- 101π105π113π

Results for Group B

Figure 6 shows the common skeleton numbering of Group A that will be employed in the results and discussion.

Figure 6: Common skeleton numbering of group B

Results for the 5-HT_{1A} receptor binding affinity of Group B.

The best equation obtained is:

$$\log(\text{IC}_{50}) = -11.20 - 0.51S_{21}^N(\text{LUMO})^* + 1.88\eta_{24} - 0.42S_{10}^N(\text{LUMO} + 2)^* + 4.90F_{13}(\text{HOMO} - 2)^* \quad (3)$$

with $n=16$, $R=0.97$, $R^2=0.94$, $\text{adj-}R^2=0.92$, $F(4,11)=41.63$ ($p<0.000001$) and a standard error of estimate of 0.23. No outliers were detected and no residuals fall outside the $\pm 2\sigma$ limits. Here, $S_{21}^N(\text{LUMO})^*$ is the nucleophilic superdelocalizability of the lowest empty MO localized on atom 21, η_{24} is the local atomic hardness of atom 24, $S_{10}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$ is the nucleophilic superdelocalizability of the third lowest empty MO localized on atom 10 and $F_{13}(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$ is the Fukui index of the third highest occupied MO localized on atom 13. Tables 9 and 10 show the beta coefficients, the results of the t-test for significance of coefficients and the matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables of Eq. 3. There are no significant internal correlations between independent variables (Table 10). Figure 7 displays the plot of observed vs. calculated $\log(\text{IC}_{50})$.

Figure 7: Plot of predicted vs. observed $\log(\text{IC}_{50})$ values (Eq. 3). Dashed lines denote the 95% confidence interval

Table 9: Beta coefficients and t-test for significance of coefficients in Eq. 3

Variable	Beta	t(11)	p-level
$S_{21}^N(\text{LUMO})^*$	-1.17	-11.17	0.000000
η_{24}	0.68	8.40	0.000004
$S_{10}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$	-0.42	-5.20	0.0003
$F_{13}(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$	0.34	3.50	0.005

Table 10: Matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables in Eq. 3

	$S_{10}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$	$F_{13}(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$	$S_{21}^N(\text{LUMO})^*$
$F_{13}(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$	0.07	1.00	
$S_{21}^N(\text{LUMO})^*$	0.12	0.41	1.00
η_{24}	0.01	0.04	0.14

The associated statistical parameters of Eq. 3 indicate that this equation is statistically significant and that the variation of the numerical values of a group of four local atomic reactivity indices of atoms of the common skeleton explains about 92% of the variation of the receptor affinity. Figure 7, spanning about 2.6 orders of magnitude, shows that there is a good correlation of observed *versus* calculated values and that almost all points are inside the 95% confidence interval.

Results for the 5-HT_{2A} receptor binding affinity of Group B.

The best equation obtained was:

$$\log(\text{IC}_{50}) = 2.07 - 0.42S_{15}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^* - 23.11F_{16}(\text{HOMO}-2)^* - 27.49F_{19}(\text{LUMO}+2)^* \quad (4)$$

with $n=10$, $R=0.99$, $R^2=0.98$, $\text{adj-}R^2=0.97$, $F(3,6)=99.07$ ($p<0.00002$) and a standard error of estimate of 0.28. No outliers were detected and no residuals fall outside the $\pm 2\sigma$ limits. Here, $S_{15}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$ is the nucleophilic superdelocalizability of the third lowest MO localized on atom 15, $F_{16}(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$ is the Fukui index of the third highest occupied MO localized on atom 16 and $F_{19}(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$ is the Fukui index of the third lowest empty MO localized on atom 19. Tables 11 and 12 show the beta coefficients, the results of the t-test for significance of coefficients and the matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables of Eq. 4. There are no significant internal correlations between independent variables (Table 12). Figure 8 displays the plot of observed *vs.* calculated $\log(\text{IC}_{50})$.

Figure 8: Plot of predicted *vs.* observed $\log(\text{IC}_{50})$ values (Eq. 4). Dashed lines denote the 95% confidence interval.

Table 11: Beta coefficients and t-test for significance of coefficients in Eq. 4

Variable	Beta	t(6)	p-level
$S_{15}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$	-0.33	-5.21	0.002
$F_{16}(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$	-0.39	-6.29	0.0007
$F_{19}(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$	-0.93	-15.49	0.000005

Table 12: Matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables in Eq. 4

	$S_{15}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^* F_{16}(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$	
$F_{16}(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$	0.13	1.00
$F_{19}(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$	0.08	0.01

The associated statistical parameters of Eq. 4 indicate that this equation is statistically significant and that the variation of the numerical values of a group of three local atomic reactivity indices of atoms of the common skeleton explains about 97% of the variation of the receptor affinity. Figure 8, spanning about 4.5 orders of magnitude, shows that there is a good correlation of observed *versus* calculated values and that almost all points are inside the 95% confidence interval.

Local Molecular Orbitals

Table 13 shows the local molecular orbitals of atoms 10, 13 and 15. Table 14 shows the local molecular orbitals of atoms 16, 19, 21 and 24 (see Fig. 6). Nomenclature: Molecule (HOMO) / (HOMO-2)* (HOMO-1)* (HOMO)* - (LUMO)* (LUMO+1)* (LUMO+2)*.

Table 13: Local Molecular Orbitals of atoms 10, 13 and 15

Molecule	Atom 10 (C)	Atom 13 (C)	Atom 15 (C)
1 (87)	80σ81σ82σ-93σ94σ95σ	74σ75σ80σ-90σ91σ92σ	74σ83σ87σ-90σ94σ95σ
2 (95)	88σ89σ90σ-102σ104σ105σ	80σ83σ88σ-98σ101σ103σ	82σ86σ93σ-98σ101σ103σ
3 (95)	87σ89σ90σ-101σ102σ103σ	81σ82σ87σ-99σ101σ102σ	80σ82σ93σ-99σ102σ103σ
4 (99)	92σ93σ94σ-105σ106σ107σ	84σ85σ92σ-103σ105σ106σ	86σ90σ98σ-103σ106σ107σ
5 (93)	86σ87σ88σ-94σ99σ101σ	78σ79σ80σ-98σ99σ101σ	80σ82σ93σ-98σ99σ102σ
6 (91)	84σ85σ86σ-97σ98σ99σ	77σ78σ84σ-94σ95σ96σ	83σ87σ91σ-94σ95σ98σ
7 (95)	88σ89σ90σ-101σ102σ103σ	80σ81σ88σ-98σ101σ102σ	84σ92σ95σ-98σ102σ103σ
8 (95)	87σ89σ90σ-101σ102σ104σ	81σ82σ87σ-99σ100σ101σ	82σ84σ91σ-98σ99σ100σ
9 (95)	87σ88σ90σ-101σ102σ103σ	81σ82σ87σ-98σ99σ100σ	82σ91σ95σ-98σ99σ100σ
10 (95)	87σ88σ89σ-101σ102σ103σ	80σ81σ87σ-98σ99σ100σ	84σ86σ91σ-98σ99σ100σ
11 (103)	94σ96σ97σ-109σ111σ112σ	87σ88σ94σ-106σ108σ109σ	88σ89σ99σ-107σ108σ110σ
12 (91)	84σ85σ86σ-97σ98σ100σ	78σ79σ84σ-96σ97σ98σ	78σ83σ91σ-96σ98σ99σ
13 (91)	84σ85σ86σ-97σ98σ99σ	79σ80σ84σ-94σ95σ96σ	80σ87σ91σ-94σ95σ96σ
14 (87)	79σ81σ82σ-93σ94σ96σ	75σ76σ79σ-91σ92σ93σ	74σ80σ87σ-91σ92σ94σ
15 (87)	81σ82σ83σ-93σ94σ95σ	75σ76σ81σ-92σ93σ94σ	78σ80σ87σ-91σ92σ94σ
16 (100)	92σ93σ94σ-106σ107σ110σ	83σ85σ92σ-105σ106σ107σ	86σ88σ98σ-105σ107σ108σ

Table 14: Local Molecular Orbitals of atoms 16, 19, 21 and 24

Molecule	Atom 16 (C)	Atom 19 (C)	Atom 21 (C)	Atom 24 (C)
1 (87)	78σ79σ83σ- 90σ91σ95σ	77σ78σ83σ- 90σ91σ92σ	83σ86π87π- 90π91π92π	83π86π87π- 90π91π92π
2 (95)	82σ91σ93σ- 97σ101σ103σ	82σ86σ93σ- 98σ101σ104σ	91π93σ95π- 97π100π101σ	87π93σ95π- 97π100π111σ
3 (95)	88σ93σ95σ- 98σ100σ105σ	80σ82σ93σ- 99σ100σ102σ	93σ94π95π- 98π100π111σ	93σ94π95π- 98π100π108σ
4 (99)	88σ97σ98σ- 102σ104σ107σ	86σ90σ98σ- 103σ104σ105σ	97π98σ99π- 102π103π104π	91π98σ99π- 102π103π104π
5 (93)	84σ90σ93σ- 95σ96σ98σ	80σ82σ93σ- 98σ102σ103σ	90π91π93σ- 95π96π100σ	84π85σ91π- 95π96π106π
6 (91)	81σ83σ87σ-	78σ81σ87σ-	87σ90π91π-	87σ90π91π-

	94σ99σ101σ	94σ95σ98σ	95π96π98π	95π96π98π
7 (95)	85σ86σ92σ-	85σ86σ92σ-	92σ94π95π-	92σ94π95π-
	99σ103σ105σ	98σ99σ102σ	98π99π100π	98π99π100π
8 (95)	88σ91σ95σ-	82σ91σ95σ-	91σ94π95π-	91σ94π95π-
	98σ100σ104σ	99σ100σ101σ	98π99π101σ	98π99π102σ
9 (95)	85σ86σ91σ-	84σ86σ91σ-	91σ94π95π-	91π94π95π-
	103σ106σ107σ	98σ99σ100σ	98π99π100π	98π99π100π
10 (95)	86σ91σ95σ-	79σ80σ91σ-	91σ93π95π-	91π93π95π-
	98σ100σ103σ	98σ99σ100σ	98π99π100π	98π99π102π
11 (103)	90σ92σ99σ-	89σ92σ99σ-	99σ102π103π-	99π102π103π-
	112σ114σ115σ	106σ107σ108σ	106π107π108π	106π107π110σ
12 (91)	83σ88σ91σ-	78σ83σ91σ-	83σ89π91σ-	83σ89π91σ-
	93σ98σ99σ	96σ98σ100σ	93π95π98σ	93π95π109σ
13 (91)	80σ82σ87σ-	80σ82σ87σ-	87σ89π91π-	87π89π91π-
	99σ101σ102σ	94σ95σ96σ	94π95π96π	94π95π96π
14 (87)	77σ80σ87σ-	75σ80σ87σ-	83π84σ87π-	83π84σ87π-
	91σ94σ97σ	91σ92σ94σ	89π91π92π	89π91π92π
15 (87)	80σ86σ87σ-	78σ80σ87σ-	81σ86σ87π-	80σ86σ87π-
	92σ95σ97σ	91σ92σ94σ	89π91π92π	89π91π92π
16 (100)	88σ95σ98σ-	86σ88σ98σ-	98σ99π100π-	95π98σ99π-
	102σ108σ109σ	105σ106σ107σ	102π104π108π	104π107π108π

Discussion

The discussion will be separated in two sections corresponding to each kind of receptor, allowing a better integration of results.

Discussion of the results of the 5-HT_{1A} receptor binding affinity of Groups A and B.

Discussion of the 5-HT_{1A} receptor binding affinity of Group A.

For group A Table 5 shows that the importance of variables in Eq. 1 is $\phi_4 \gg S_{12}^E(\text{HOMO}-2)^* \gg F_4(\text{LUMO})^* > S_{19}^E$. In the following discussions we shall employ the approximate variable-by-variable (VbV) method. By considering the sign associated to each variable in Eq. 1 together with the positive or negative value of the local atomic reactivity indices, a high receptor affinity is associated with small values of ϕ_4 , large (negative) values of S_{19}^E , small (negative) values of $S_{12}^E(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$ and large values of $F_4(\text{LUMO})^*$. ϕ_4 is the orientational parameter of the R₄ substituent. A small value of the OP demands a small substituent, like H. Table 1 suggests that, for getting more information about the nature of an appropriate R₄ substituent, a methyl group will be apt. Another possibility is simply substituting the carbon atom 22 by a nitrogen atom. On the other hand we need to consider that the modification of R₄ must not alter in a significant way the electronic structure of the system. Atom 12 is a hydrogen atom attached to N9 (see Fig. 3). All local MOs are of σ nature (Table 7). In all molecules the local (HOMO)₁₂^{*} is situated very far from the corresponding molecular HOMO (Table 7). Small (negative) values of $S_{12}^E(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$ are associated with high receptor affinity. Small values for this index are obtained by lowering the associated eigenvalue and/or by lowering the electron population of this MO. On this basis we suggest that the H atom is participating in an N-H...X hydrogen bond. Atom 4 is a carbon atom in ring A (Fig. 3). A high receptor affinity is associated with large values of $F_4(\text{LUMO})^*$. Table 7 shows that the local (LUMO)₄^{*} has a π nature and that it coincides with the molecular LUMO. Note also that all (HOMO)₄^{*} have a σ nature in all molecules. Therefore, we suggest that atom 4 is interacting with an electron rich center, possible of the π - π kind. Atom 19 is a carbon atom in ring C (Fig. 3). A high receptor affinity is associated with large (negative) values of S_{19}^E , suggesting that this atom is acting as an electron donor. All the above suggestions are displayed in the partial 2D pharmacophore of Fig. 9.

Figure 9: Partial 2D pharmacophore for the 5-HT_{1A} binding affinity of group A.

Discussion of the 5-HT_{1A} receptor binding affinity of Group B.

For group B Table 9 shows that the importance of variables in Eq. 3 is $S_{21}^N(\text{LUMO})^* > \eta_{24} > S_{10}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^* > F_{13}(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$. By considering the sign associated to each variable in Eq. 3 together with the positive or negative value of the local atomic reactivity indices, we can see that a high receptor affinity is associated with a small value for η_{24} and a small value for $F_{13}(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$. If $S_{21}^N(\text{LUMO})^*$ is positive, a high receptor affinity is associated with a high numerical value for this reactivity index. The same holds for the case of a positive value for $S_{10}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$. Atom 21 is a carbon in ring C (Fig. 6). Table 14 shows that $(\text{LUMO})_{21}^*$ has a π nature in all molecules. A high receptor affinity is associated with high numerical values for $S_{21}^N(\text{LUMO})^*$. These values are obtained by lowering the energy of this MO, making it more reactive. Therefore, it is suggested that this atom is interacting with an electron-rich center (probably through a π - π interaction). Atom 24 is a carbon in ring C (Fig. 6). A high receptor affinity is associated with low numerical values for this local atomic hardness, η_{24} (the $\text{HOMO}^*-\text{LUMO}^*$ energy gap). It is almost always a positive number (it has a zero value in the case of metals and in some atoms of semimetals). If we interpret the local atomic hardness as the resistance of an atom to exchange electrons with the milieu, a small value indicates that, for a higher receptor affinity, atom 24 should be more reactive. Now, Table 14 shows that in almost all molecules the local HOMO^* coincides with the molecular HOMO , while the local LUMO^* corresponds to higher empty molecular MOs. Then, the only way to get a smaller $\text{HOMO}^*-\text{LUMO}^*$ energy gap is by shifting downwards the LUMO^* eigenvalue energy. This suggests that atom 24 is interacting with an electron-rich center. Atom 10 is a saturated carbon in the chain linking N9 with ring B (Fig. 6). All local MOs have σ nature (Table 13). If $S_{21}^N(\text{LUMO})^*$ is positive, then a high affinity is associated with high numerical values for this index. These values are obtained by shifting downwards the MO eigenvalue; making the MO more reactive.

Figure 10: Partial 2D pharmacophore for the 5-HT_{1A} binding affinity of group B

On this basis we suggest that atom 10 is interacting with an electron-rich center. Atom 13 is a saturated carbon in the chain linking N9 with ring B (Fig. 6). All local MOs have σ nature (Table 13). As $F_{13}(\text{HOMO-2})^*$ is always positive, a high affinity is associated with a low electron population on this local MO*. We may observe also in Table 14 that the three highest occupied local MOs of atom 13 are far below from the molecule's HOMO, suggesting that this atom cannot act as an electron donor. Therefore, we suggest that atom 13 is interacting with an electron-rich center. All the above suggestions are displayed in the partial 2D pharmacophore of Fig. 10.

Discussion of the results of the 5-HT_{2A} receptor binding affinity of Groups A and B.

Discussion of the 5-HT_{2A} receptor binding affinity of Group A.

For group A Table 5 shows that the importance of variables in Eq. 2 is $S_8^E(\text{HOMO-1})^* > F_{15}(\text{HOMO-2})^* > S_{23}^N(\text{LUMO+2})^* > \mu_{10} > F_{21}(\text{HOMO-1})^*$. Analyzing the sign associated with each variable in Eq. 2 together with the positive or negative value of the local atomic reactivity indices, we can see that a high receptor affinity is associated with low numerical values for $S_8^E(\text{HOMO-1})^*$ (that is always a negative number), high numerical values for $F_{15}(\text{HOMO-2})^*$ (that is always a positive number), small numerical values for μ_{10} (that is always a negative number) and small numerical values for $F_{21}(\text{HOMO-1})^*$. If $S_{23}^N(\text{LUMO+2})^*$ is a positive number, then a high affinity is associated with small numerical values for this index. Atom 8 is a carbonyl oxygen atom in the chain linking rings A and B (Fig. 3). Table 7 shows that the three lowest empty and the three highest occupied MOs have π nature and that only the local LUMO* coincides with the molecular LUMO. Small negative values for $S_8^E(\text{HOMO-1})^*$ are obtained by lowering the $(\text{HOMO-1})_8^*$ energy, making this MO less reactive. This allows us to suggest that atom 8 is interacting with the receptor as an electron acceptor. Atom 15 is a saturated carbon atom in ring B (Fig. 3). Table 7 shows that all local MOs have σ nature. High numerical values for $F_{15}(\text{HOMO-2})^*$ are obtained by increasing the electron population on this MO. This suggests that atom 15 is interacting with an electron deficient center. Atom 10 is a saturated carbon atom in the chain linking rings A and B (Fig. 3). Table 7 shows that all local MOs have σ nature. μ_{10} is the local atomic electronic chemical potential of atom 10. A high affinity is associated with small numerical negative values for μ_{10} . For reasons exposed in another paper [37], the best way to get these values is by shifting upwards the energy of the local LUMO*; making this MO less reactive. Therefore, we suggest that atom 10 is interacting with an electron-deficient center. This coincides with the standard interpretation stating that a small negative value of this index implies a good electron donor. Atom 23 is a carbon atom in ring C (Fig. 3). Table 8 shows that all molecules but one the local HOMO*s of this atom have π nature. If $S_{23}^N(\text{LUMO+2})^*$ is positive, a high affinity is related to small numerical values for this index. These values are obtained by shifting upwards the energy of this local MO; making it less reactive. This suggests that this atom is interacting with an electron-deficient center. Atom 21 is a carbon atom in ring C (Fig. 3). Table 8 shows that all molecules but one the local $(\text{HOMO-1})^*$ s of this atom have π nature. The analysis of this index suggests that this atom is interacting with an electron-rich center. All the above suggestions are displayed in the partial 2D pharmacophore of Fig. 11.

Figure 11: Partial 2D pharmacophore for the 5-HT_{2A} binding affinity of group A

Discussion of the 5-HT_{2A} receptor binding affinity of Group B.

For group B Table 11 shows that the importance of variables in Eq. 4 is $F_{19}(\text{LUMO}+2)^* \gg F_{16}(\text{HOMO}-2)^* > S_{15}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$. Analyzing the sign associated with each variable in Eq. 4 and the positive or negative value of the local atomic reactivity indices, we can see that a high 5-HT_{2A} receptor affinity is associated with small numerical values for $F_{16}(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$ and $F_{19}(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$. If the numerical value of $S_{15}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$ is positive, then a high affinity is associated with high numerical values for this index. Atom 15 is a carbon in ring B (Fig. 6). All local MOs have σ nature (Table 13). High positive numerical values for this index are obtained by shifting downwards the value corresponding eigenvalue; making this MO more reactive. Therefore, it is suggested that atom 15 is interacting with an electron-rich center. Atom 16 is a carbon in ring B (Fig. 6). All local MOs have σ nature (Table 14). Small numerical values for $F_{16}(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$ are obtained by incrementing the electron population of $(\text{HOMO}-2)_{16}^*$. Accordingly to this, atom 16 should be interacting with an electron-deficient center. Atom 19 is a carbon in ring B (Fig. 6). All local MOs have σ nature (Table 14). Small numerical values for $F_{19}(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$ are obtained by diminishing the electron population of $(\text{LUMO}+2)_{19}^*$. Therefore, it is suggested that atom 19 is interacting with an electron-deficient center. All the above suggestions are displayed in the partial 2D pharmacophore of Fig. 12.

Figure 12: Partial 2D pharmacophore for the 5-HT_{2A} binding affinity of group B

Integration of pharmacophores.

For both series of molecules we may integrate the partial 2D pharmacophores for the binding to each receptor to have an approximate view of what could be happening. For the integration, we have assumed that rings A and C (the aromatic ones) of both series of molecules bind to the same sites of the receptor.

2D pharmacophore integration for 5-HT_{1A} binding.

Figure 13 shows the integrated pharmacophore.

Figure 13: Partial 2D integrated pharmacophore for 5-HT_{1A} binding of groups A and B.

The integrated partial pharmacophore allow suggesting that rings A and C are interacting with sites having π electrons (aromatic rings, carboxylate moieties, etc.). In a recent analysis of the interaction of 2,5-dimethoxyphenethylamines and their N-2-methoxybenzyl-substituted analogs with 5-HT_{1A} serotonin receptors[1] it was suggested that the methanediyl groups of the ethylamine side chain seemed to interact with a site or sites having sigma electrons. If the integration presented here is correct, then we are again in presence of a three dimensional receptor site having occupied σ MOs (in ancient chemistry these sites were called sometimes “hydrophobic pockets”). The appearance in ring C of three carbon atoms strongly suggests that this ring is involved in π - π aromatic interactions with the receptor.

2D pharmacophore integration for 5-HT_{2A} binding.

Figure 14 shows the integrated pharmacophore.

Figure 14: Partial 2D integrated pharmacophore for 5-HT_{2A} binding of groups A and B.

The analysis of Fig. 14 again suggests the presence of a site rich in sigma electrons but now in the 5-HT_{2A} receptor. Again ring C seems to interact with a site through π - π interactions. This similitude between the integrated pharmacophores suggests two possibilities. The first one states that this is only a mere coincidence. The second one states that both receptors have a similar binding volume conserved during evolution.

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